

USING INNOVATIVE METHODS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Annotations: This article discusses the importance of using innovative technologies in teaching the English language in schools in Uzbekistan today. There is also information about "Work in small groups", "Brainstorming", "Problem learning technology", "Blitz game method", "Boomerang" technology.

Key words: innovation, learning, method, small group, mental attack, problem learning, blitz game, boomerang, discussion.

Today, an innovative approach to the educational process is becoming a requirement of the time. The innovative approach is to use various interactive methods during this course. Each lesson organized using such methods contributes to greater activity of students and increase their interest in science. With the help of the interactive method, the interaction between the teacher and the student takes place. During the lesson, students try to master the topic on their own, they get motivated, they learn to think collectively and individually. In the process of teaching Russian to schoolchildren in Uzbek schools, the use of new pedagogical technologies, interactive methods gives good results. The lesson can be organized in an unconventional way: competitions, debates, travel lessons, conferences and demonstration lessons. They also help us in conducting the educational process using interactive methods, such as "Work in small groups", "Brainstorming", "Problem learning technology", "Blitz game method", "Boomerang" technology. ladies. "Small group work" is an interactive method that divides students into several groups and assigns tasks to them, thereby determining how active they are in team thinking. Some students may express ideas and actions that they could not express on their own in a small group. In a lesson organized using this

method, groups can be given the same or different tasks. At the same time, it is necessary to closely monitor the activities of students. In it, students learn to participate in discussions, listen to the opinions of others. They create live communication.

Brainstorming is a method of gathering free ideas and feedback from students about a problem and finding a solution. There are written and oral forms of brainstorming. Each student verbally expresses his opinion on the question posed by the teacher orally. Students write their answers clearly and concisely. In writing, they record their responses on a piece of paper in a concise and visual way. Answers are attached on the blackboard (using magnets) to the blackboard (using pins). In writing, brainstorming answers can be grouped according to certain characteristics. When used correctly and positively, this method teaches a person to think freely, creatively and outside the box. Problem-based learning technology is the most natural and effective way of learning, since the logic of scientific knowledge embodies the logic of problem situations.

Problem solving situations are presented, and traditional narration is the most optimal content of educational material. The teacher creates a problem situation, directs the student to solve it, organizes the search for a solution. Problem learning management requires pedagogical skills, since the emergence of a problem situation is an individual situation and requires a differentiated and individual approach. Problem-based learning technology is the most natural and effective way of learning, since the logic of scientific knowledge embodies the logic of problem situations.

Problem solving situations are presented, and traditional narration is the most optimal content of educational material. The teacher creates a problem situation, directs the student to solve it, organizes the search for a solution. Problem learning management requires pedagogical skills, since the emergence of a problem situation is an individual situation and requires a differentiated and individual approach. Boomerang technology - this technology is aimed at a deep and holistic study of the material in one lesson, creative reflection, free assimilation. Suitable for studying topics of different content and nature (problematic, controversial, different content),

includes oral and written forms of work, as well as different tasks for each participant during one lesson. can be played as a student and teacher, respectively. This technology allows you to think critically, form logic; develops memory, ideas, thoughts, arguments in written and oral forms. Along with training, this method allows you to perform a number of tasks of an educational nature. Teamwork skills; problem solving, cheerfulness, adaptability, respect for dissent, activism, the formation of leadership qualities, a creative approach to work, an interest in the effectiveness of their activities, self-esteem. Basic concepts:

Open-ended questions are questions that allow you to communicate and keep the conversation going. Briefly them. It is impossible to give the same answer. Closed questions are those in which the answers to the questions are given correctly, openly or in the form of "yes" or "no".

Cross-examination is a series of short questions asked of each other in groups, which provides an excellent opportunity to find specific information and determine the facts, position of opponents and make specific decisions. During cross-examination, it is impossible to start a discussion. Currently, only questions are being asked, there is no discussion.

The choice of an interactive method that is appropriate for the topic and student audience in the classroom depends on the skill of the teacher. The main task of the educator is to be a manager. It controls the process of formation, development, knowledge and education of the individual. Management is the process of directing, appointing, teaching, helping, supporting, advising, guiding, observing, demanding, and instructing.

Links:

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